

Review

What Benefits Does Generative Artificial Intelligence Technology Confer in K-12 Education?

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Abstract

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) is a recent development in the 21st century, and is changing classrooms throughout the world. However, its role in K–12 settings remain underexplored compared to higher education. This review paper examines how GAI can support teaching and learning in classrooms by personalizing instruction, assisting teachers with planning and reflection, and expanding access to high-quality learning experiences. Furthermore, this paper analyzes teacher and student perspectives, implementation challenges, and reviews concerns about overreliance, academic integrity, and equity. These findings suggest that clear policies, careful introduction to students, and instructional supervision are necessary to successful implementation in K-12 schools. At the same time, technology access disparities between students and risks to independent thinking show the need for caution while integrating GAI into instruction. Overall, this paper argues the importance of appropriate oversight and ethical frameworks in the implementation of GAI. With caution, GAI can enhance, rather than replace, important elements in K-12 education.

Keywords: *K-12 Education, Generative AI, Learning, Teaching, Educational Technology*

Introduction

As technology changes, other fields must also change, including education. Recent technological advancements in the 21st century brought major changes to education, influencing the way teachers teach and students learn (Samuel et al., 2014). Among these innovations, Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) holds much promise to transform the K-12 education system by personalizing instruction, supporting teachers, and expanding access to a high-quality learning experience. This paper focuses on the benefits that GAI can provide in a K-12 environment for teachers and students. There is much research regarding how GAI can improve higher education (i.e. college/university level), however there is a need to understand how GAI can have an impact on the K-12 level. In addition, there are varying opinions on GAI depending on grade level within the K-12 grades, with elementary school teachers requiring management/organizational assistance, and middle and high school teachers needing help with lesson planning and self-reflection (Kyoungwon, et al., 2025). The use of Generative Artificial Intelligence within K-12 classrooms should be monitored carefully to ensure misuse does not occur, however, its use can be beneficial to both students and teachers. This paper investigates, through a cultural/social perspective, how Generative Artificial Intelligence can be effectively integrated into K-12 classrooms while balancing educational benefits with concerns surrounding misuse, equity, and student development.

Assertion #1

Policies and procedures need to be set in place for successful implementation of GAI in K-12 classrooms. A study that conducted qualitative research from face-to-face interviews with 10 kindergarten teachers corroborated the claim that policies should be set in place to manage GAI use, because without a clear framework for use, teachers will use it for different purposes/causes, leading to a disarray (Su, Jiahong, and Weipeng Yang, 2024). Another study (Giannakos, Michail, et al., 2025) focused

on the potential benefits that using GAI in the classroom confers, as well as its challenges. The authors (reputable researchers at the Department of Computer Science in the Norwegian University of Science and Technology) all concurred that there should be a sort of skeptical optimism, and even a slight precaution, to using Generative Artificial Intelligence in education, because of potential misuse that could be harmful to students. This source bolsters the claim of policies for successful implementation, because it shows that GAI use should be closely monitored to prevent misuse. Overall, the evidence conclusively claims that the use of GAI should be monitored to ensure proper use.

Assertion #2

To ensure successful implementation of Generative Artificial Intelligence, students must support and approve the use of it first. This claim takes into consideration the perspective of students, and not just teachers, due to the fact that they are the other half of education. One study, performed by Stanford University researchers, on middle school students' perspectives regarding the use of GAI showed a plurality of responses (Ibrahim Oluwajoba Adisa and Adenike Omolara Adefisayo, 2025). This source asserts that middle schoolers believe that GAI can be useful if they gain autonomy over use. Another study on the factors influencing engagement in AI use for education showed similar results (Li, Wei, et al., 2024). The authors, who are credible researchers at Kookmin University in Seoul, believe that "cognitive factors" or the way that Generative Artificial Intelligence is introduced to students is important. The authors also, through a survey of 197 respondents, found that intrinsic motivation to use AI and better UI can improve usability. Overall, the evidence supports the claim that AI use should be implemented correctly and in an effective manner to be successful.

Assertion #3

While GAI has the potential to expand access to high-quality instruction, disparities in technology access across school districts may limit its benefits for many students, potentially exacerbating existing educational inequities. The digital divide, which is defined as the gap between those who have reliable access to digital tools and those who do not, remains a large barrier for many low-income, rural, and underserved communities. As one source notes, “marginalized groups...are often disproportionately affected by the digital divide, limiting their ability to access online learning platforms, AI tools, and digital skills training programs” (Farahani and Ghasemi, 2024). This means that students in under-resourced districts may be unable to use GAI tools for personalized learning, tutoring, or skill development at the same level as their peers in wealthier schools. In addition, students may lack the necessary digital literacy needed to use such AI tools effectively, and schools without strong technology programs would struggle to prepare them. Furthermore, due to the fact that most GAI models require large datasets to train and function, student privacy is at risk. A paper published in the journal *Frontiers of Education* highlights the risk of data leaks, especially related to student academic performance. The paper claims that if “... this data is leaked or misused, it will seriously affect students’ personal privacy and security,” since it may link to students’ private information/details (Yu and Guo, 2023).

Assertion #4

Despite the potential benefits of Generative Artificial Intelligence in K–12 education, critics argue that its integration poses significant risks to student learning and development. One major concern is frequent reliance on GAI may discourage independent thinking and problem-solving, particularly among younger students who are still developing foundational academic skills. A study analyzing GAI reliance for students in finding the answers to midterm and final exams in a university located in Indonesia found that “70% of students utilized AI occasionally or frequently to complete exams, citing efficiency and ease

of access” (Adiyono Adiyono et al., 2025). The authors claim that only 30% of these students believe AI supports an in-depth understanding of material. Furthermore, the authors contend that a reduction of student analytical skill comes from an overuse of GAI. A 2024 literature review of 14 scientific articles asserted that students prefer optimal solutions that don’t require much work (taking the easy route), instead of slow routes that would be more practical, and turn to GAI for convenience (Zhai et al., 2024). The authors claim that this leads to an impact on cognitive ability, especially decision-making and analytical reasoning. In addition to the reliance of GAI, critics also warn that the ease with which GAI can generate complete responses may increase academic dishonesty and reduce students’ motivation to engage deeply with coursework. It is important we address these issues for the use of GAI as we implement it in classrooms. These concerns highlight the importance of carefully considering the unintended consequences of implementing GAI in classrooms without clear guidelines and instructional oversight.

Conclusion

In summary, GAI can be successful in the classroom if implemented correctly. As Generative Artificial Intelligence continues to evolve, future research should focus on long-term learning outcomes, ethical implementation, and age-appropriate usage guidelines. With thoughtful oversight and inclusive policy development, GAI has the potential to become a powerful tool that enhances, not replaces, important learning in K–12 education. The studies cited in this paper were conducted by credible researchers at well-renowned universities and institutions, published in peer-reviewed journals. Research supports the idea that GAI can be used if there are policies to manage use, and students as well as teachers agree with the use of it. Many researchers claim that students and teachers should not rely on Generative Artificial Intelligence because it can lead to them not being able to perform certain tasks well

enough or at all. However, we must think of cultural change, and how change can lead to better outcomes. Perhaps the use of GAI in K-12 education can be useful to both students and teachers.

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